

Targeting pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma-on-a-chip with aptamer-guided extracellular vesicle delivery.

Version 1

Description

Within the framework of Latvian Council of Science grant No. lzp-2024/1-0206 researchers from University of Latvia and Biomedical Research and Study center aim to develop targeted drug delivery approach using GreenB1 aptamer and extracellular vesicle (EV) conjugate towards human PDAC-derived organoids in an organ-on-chip platform.

Data packages published will include data on GreenB1 selectivity and specificity towards PDAC in static cell culture and in PDAC-on-chip system, characterization data of mesenchymal stem cell derived (MSC)-EVs and GreenB1 conjugated MSC-EVs as well as data of MSC-EV-GreenB1 assessment in PDAC-on-chip system.

The intended project period is 2025-2028.

Funder

Latvian Council of Sciences

Grant

Targeting pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma-on-a-chip with

aptamer-guided extracellular
vesicle delivery (Izp-2024/1-
0206)

Researchers

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1836-3999), Liga Kunrade (orcid:0000-0001-8890-7560)

Organizations

Latvian Biomedical Research and Study Centre, University of
Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Targeting pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma-on-a-chip with aptamer-guided extracellular vesicle delivery.

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Organizations:

Latvian Biomedical Research and Study Centre

University of Latvia

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Sciences

Grants: Targeting pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma-on-a-chip with aptamer-guided extracellular vesicle delivery (lzp-2024/1-0206)

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date: 2024-12-03

4. Templates

Descriptions

GreenB1 affinity and selectivity towards PDAC.

Data in this data set will be in line with the pre-set project objective:

1. Development of PDAC-on-chip and validation of GreenB1 specificity and affinity towards PDAC

organoids and normal pancreatic cell cultures in vitro.

It includes selectivity and affinity testing of GreenB1 aptamer towards PDAC organoids and normal pancreatic cultures in vitro using flow cytometry and immunofluorescence.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The purpose is to assess if IntegrinB1 is overexpressed in primary PDAC samples in comparison to primary normal pancreatic tissue. It will be done by antibody and subsequently by GreenB1 aptamer with a fluorescent label. To assess further aptamer transport in a microfluidic system, primary characterization of the affinity and specificity is required.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- PDF
- TIFF
- XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

200

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

To other researchers in the field of cell biology, cancer biology and aptamer research.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Till 01.06.2028.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

zenodo

<https://zenodo.org>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

MS Excell, any PDF reader.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2028-01-01

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Liga Kunrade (orcid: [0000-0001-8890-7560](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8890-7560))

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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